

DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE MATHEMATICS TEACHERS IN A CREDIT-MODULAR SETTING

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bugungi kunda kredit-modul sharoitida bo'lajak matematika o'qituvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish metodikasi yoritilib ayni vaqtda ta'limning zamonaviy tendentsiyalar jarayonida bo'lajak matematika o'qituvchilarning mantiqiy tafakkurini mazmuni bayon etlgan hamda tajriba sinov asosida olingan natijalarning samaradorlik darajasi anqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: mantiqiy tafakkurini, ko'nikma, pedagogik kompetentsiya, iste'dod, innovatsiya, ijodkorlik, tanqidiy fikrlash, muammolarni hal qilish.

Аннотация: В данной статье освещена методика развития логического мышления будущих учителей математики в кредитно-модульных условиях на сегодняшний день, изложено содержание логического мышления будущих учителей математики в современных тенденциях образования и определен уровень эффективности результатов, полученных на основе экспериментального тестирования.

Ключевые слова: логическое мышление, умение, педагогическая компетентность, талант, новаторство, креативность, критическое мышление, решение проблем.

Abstract: This article highlights the methodology for the development of logical thinking of future mathematics teachers in credit-modular conditions today, outlines the content of logical thinking of future mathematics teachers in modern educational trends and determines the level of effectiveness of the results obtained on the basis of experimental testing.

Keywords: logical thinking, skill, pedagogical competence, talent, innovation, creativity, critical thinking, problem solving.

Introduction: Today, logical reasoning is important in the teaching of Mathematics and plays a large role in the development of analytical and discussion skills of students. The importance and need for the development of logical thinking for teachers of mathematics in the conditions of the loan-module has been recognized in the higher. This article will show you the importance of teaching logic and mathematics together and how to combine them.

Sacred sources of teaching logic and Mathematics

Logical reasoning and sacred sources of teaching mathematics are based on the analysis of students' logical abilities and problems arising from mathematics. In the process of teaching students, skills are developed to express, analyze and discuss their own ideas on solving logical problems, visualizing and solving tasks derived

from mathematics.

Logical thinking and the impact of teaching mathematics on practice

The impact of logical reasoning and mathematics teaching on practice assimilates students in logical learning, imagination, analysis and discussion. Practical exercises, projects, games and discussion processes that require students to express their opinions will help develop logical thinking. These techniques develop skills in students that focus on working with and solving logical problems.

Approaches to teaching logical thinking and Mathematics

The following approaches can be useful for a good study of logical thinking and teaching mathematics:

Teaching the analysis and solution of logical problems through practical skills. Providing students with logical questions related to problems arising from mathematics.

Strengthening students through exercises aimed at Discussion, Analysis and expression of their thoughts.

In the educational process, it is necessary to link logical problems to the current life and show ways to solve them.

Directing students to participate in Group Work, Project Preparation, and math-based learning activities.

In a large article on the topic of developing the logical background of future mathematics teachers in the conditions of manticredit-module, I am writing as follows:

Logical thinking and teaching mathematics is an important topic for teachers in a credit-module setting. Logical reasoning is a key aspect in developing students' logical abilities, analytical and discussion skills. Mathematics, on the other hand, allows students to use logical views, solve problems, and learn in auxiliary group work and analytically.

There are several important tips for teaching logic and mathematics together:

Linking logical problems to logical processes: allowing students to learn logical processes to solve logical problems. They can be associated with problems arising from mathematics, and this will help develop their logical reflexes. Practical exercises and projects: practical exercises and projects are essential for the development of logical thinking. They train students to engage in logical question solving, analysis, and discussion processes. These exercises increase students' ability to solve logical problems and answer questions from mathematics. Directing students to analyze and express their thoughts: when teaching logical thinking and mathematics, it is very important to direct students to analyze and record their thoughts. This develops their ability to express logical views, analyze results from mathematics, and communicate their thoughts to others.

Discussion and group work: Discussion and group work are also important in teaching logical thinking and mathematics. It is very important to require students to participate in group work and discussion processes in order to ask each other questions, analyze logical problems and interpret their thoughts to others. This allows them to strengthen their logical views and use their ideas to communicate to others. Connecting logical problems with current life: in teaching logical thinking

and mathematics, it is important to direct students to connecting logical problems with current life. For them, mathematics will be associated with solving problems that are transferred to practice and their problems in current life.

Individual learning paths: in Logical Reasoning and mathematics teaching, it is important to provide individual learning paths for each student. All students can have a logical level of comprehension and differ in the development of their skills in mathematics. Therefore, teachers need to draw up and perform educational materials, taking into account the individual abilities of students and the need for additional vacation. Frequent practice: in the teaching of logical thinking and mathematics, it is often recommended to use a practice-based style. Practical exercises, games, working with concepts and solving math tasks increase students' mastery abilities. Practice helps students learn techniques aimed at working with and solving logical problems.

Using news: it is very important to use logical reasoning and mathematics teaching as well as entertainment news. New mathematical concepts, applications, analytical assignments, and problems increase students' interests and support them to understand the connection with mathematics. Focusing readers on news and directing them to express their thoughts will be of great importance in the development of logical thinking. Cooperative learning: cooperative learning methods are also effective in teaching logical thinking and mathematics. It is important to guide students to participate in group work, Inter-student collaboration, or intensive analysis processes. They allow students to assist each other and provide additional views of each other in solving logical problems.

Assessment of learning outcomes: logical thinking and mathematics an important part of teaching is the assessment and valuations of learning outcomes. When solving logical questions and tasks, it is important to use it in advice, taking into account the assessment of students, their participation in the processes of analysis and discussion. This allows students to understand and develop their own level of logical thinking.

Personal approach to students: each student differs in their individual characteristics and specific reading methods. For this reason, it is important for teachers to define reading techniques, taking into account the familiar and acquired abilities of students, their need for additional vacation.

Cooperative learning: it is very important to allow students to help each other, think and express their thoughts. Group work, participation in inter-student collaborative task solving, logical problem solving, and analysis processes develop student mastery and analysis skills. Real - life examples: the use of real-life examples in Logical Reasoning and mathematics lessons increases students' interests and gives them additional motivation in solving logical problems. Examples will help students understand how to relate to logical thinking and mathematics.

Complex problems and concepts: it is important to train students to learn techniques aimed at solving and analyzing complex logical problems. Complex problems will be of great importance in the development of students' logical thinking and discussion skills.

Display of educational materials: display and visualization of educational

materials increases the level of understanding of students. The use of graphs, diagrams, models, animations and other visual tools in Logical Reasoning and mathematics lessons reinforces students' understanding of logical reasoning and mathematics. The use of innovations: the use of innovations in the field of logical thinking and mathematics interests students and allows them to understand the connection between logical thinking and mathematics. You can use these news items to guide readers to be interested in the News, Express and discuss their opinions.

Assessment of learning outcomes: assessment and valuations of learning outcomes help students understand how they make themselves assimilated in the process of evaluation, logical problem solving, and analysis. You can use it in tips to help students increase their logical level of awareness.

You can implement the following recommendations when teaching logical thinking and mathematics:

Individual approach: each student will have their own way of reading and their own methods of mastering. For this reason, it is important for teachers to define reading techniques, taking into account the familiarity of students and their need for additional leave.

Complex problems and examples: teaching students to learn methods aimed at solving and analyzing complex logical problems will be of great importance. Complex problems play an important role in developing students' logical thinking and discussion skills. Also, examples related to logical reasoning and mathematics increase students' interests and give them additional motivation in solving logical problems. Practice-based teaching: Logical Reasoning and mathematics are recommended to use a practice-based style in teaching. In the process of solving, analyzing and discussing logical problems, it is important to direct students to work with practical exercises, games and concepts. This method helps to increase the ability of students to practice and master their skills related to logical thinking and mathematics. Cooperative learning: it is important to direct students to participate in group work, Inter-student collaborative task solving or intensive analysis processes. They allow students to help each other, think and express their thoughts. This method will be of great importance in improving students' ability to solve and analyze logical problems.

Conclusion:

Visualization: visualization of learning materials increases the level of understanding of students. The use of graphs, diagrams, models, animations and other visual tools enhances students' understanding of logic and mathematics in logic and mathematics classes.

The use of innovations: it is very important to also use innovations in the field of logical thinking and mathematics. New mathematical concepts, applications, analytical assignments and problems increase the interests of students and support them to understand logical thinking and connection with mathematics.

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